

Overview and key considerations for establishing a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) for global health research

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Purpose of this document

This document aims to provide a high-level introduction to the principles, benefits, and key considerations involved in setting up and maintaining Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for global health research. It highlights the role of TREs in safeguarding data security and integrity for global health research purposes. The target audience of this resource includes global health research institutes, networks, and research communities seeking to understand or establish TREs.

This resource draws insights from:

- The [UK Health Data Research Alliance's](#) publication '[Building Trusted Research Environments - Principles and Best Practices; Towards TRE ecosystems](#)' and other related [outputs](#).
- Health Data Research UK's experiences in convening the [Data and Connectivity](#) programme, [DARE UK](#) and its [SATRE specification](#) project, and the [HDR Global](#) and [ICODA](#) programmes

Trusted Environments (TREs) are highly secure computing environments that protect - by design - the privacy of individuals whose health data they hold, whilst facilitating large-scale data analysis using optional High-Performance Computing. TREs protect privacy and maintain security while helping make research efficient, collaborative and cost effective, providing rich data that enables deep insights to help improve healthcare and save lives¹. TREs are also sometimes known as Secure Data Environments (SDEs), Data Safe Havens, or

¹ <https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/access-to-health-data/trusted-research-environments/>

Secure Processing Environments (SPEs), amongst other terms. A TRE encompasses more than just the technical infrastructure; this document also addresses the operational aspects, data governance, and support functions integral to a TRE solution.

Benefits of TREs

TREs offer a range of benefits that extend beyond security and data governance. They support collaboration, facilitate data access, and can enable powerful computing resources for advanced data analysis and research. The following diagram details some of the key benefits TREs can provide.

Trusted Research Environments can be tailored to support a wide range of features and tools. Some common examples are shown below.

Enabling trustworthy data governance through the “Five Safes” model

To keep data secure, TREs are typically guided in the UK by the Five Safes framework², a set of overlapping principles designed to ensure safe and secure access to data for researchers where any failure in one area is mitigated by the others³. The Five Safes - Safe people, Safe projects, Safe settings, Safe outputs, Safe data - should be considered as adjustable controls, rather than binary settings. Risk is addressed by complementary adjustments on the implementation of each “Safe” to provide an appropriate context for research to occur, which maintains an optimal balance between research benefit and overall risk management. The following diagram describes each of the Five Safes.

TREs are integral to this framework by providing “Safe Settings” where research can be conducted safely and securely, and in doing so, support the other components of the Five Safes model. TREs provide the technical mechanisms to restrict data access to authorised individuals only, aligning with the “Safe People” control. This ensures that those who have access to the TRE and its data are appropriately vetted, trained and authorised, including TRE staff responsible for managing infrastructure, maintaining security, providing user support, and overseeing data access and usage. The “Safe Projects” principle is supported through TREs by providing project-specific permissions and access controls, ensuring that specific data is accessible only to authorised users within defined project workspaces. TREs also support the “Safe Data” principle by enabling sensitive and complex data to be curated and de-identified, ensuring that it is prepared and protected appropriately for research purposes. Finally, TREs reinforce the “Safe Outputs” principle by ensuring that data cannot

² Ritchie F. *Five Safes: Designing Data Access for Research.*; 2016. doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.3661.1604

³ <https://www.researchdata.scot/our-work/data-explainers/what-are-trusted-research-environments/>

be exported from the environment unless it passes through disclosure control checks and is released via approved mechanisms, such as encrypted Secure File Transfer Protocol.

The following diagram shows an example schematic of a TRE with labels for the Five Safes.

A notable project that established a Trusted Research Environment to support global health research is the [International COVID-19 Data Alliance \(ICODA\) programme](#). ICODA adopted the Five Safes framework to guide the development of governance and review policies, ensuring trustworthy use of data within its TRE. Generic, open, and free to use versions of these policies can be found on the [ICODA Publications and Outputs](#) page.

The requirements gathering process

When looking to establish a new Trusted Research Environment as part of a research institute or network, it is important to conduct a comprehensive requirements gathering process. This involves carefully considering and addressing all relevant aspects of the solution, including technology infrastructure, information governance, data management, supporting services, as well as time, cost, and staff requirements. Initiating this process around some proof-of-concept projects based on typical use cases can also help in addressing these aspects and familiarise the TRE team with the environment.

This approach will ensure that the chosen or developed solution not only fulfils the current research needs, but also serves as a flexible foundation that can be adapted and expanded upon to meet the future requirements of the research network.

The requirements gathering process should include essential criteria related to the research objectives, data, governance and legal governance considerations, as well as the associated operational and resource considerations. This should also involve engaging with and considering the perspectives of a diverse range of TRE stakeholders, including researchers, data managers, data owners/custodians, data controllers, as well as members of the public and local communities, health practitioners and policy makers.

To initiate the process of capturing and shaping the requirements of the Trusted Research Environment, the following perspectives and questions may be considered:

Perspectives	Example questions
Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How will researchers be using the TRE and for what purposes? What types of studies and research questions will be conducted within the TRE? ● Will the researchers be from multiple organisations in one country or multiple countries? ● What will the TRE enable? (e.g. greater access to data for research, greater linkage of key datasets, greater collaboration across countries and regions) ● How will researchers be 'accredited'? How many researchers will be using the platform?
Data management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What types of data will be accessed, processed, and stored within the TRE? (e.g. HDSS and other cohort data, patient health records, administration data, lab data, imaging, genomic/omics data) ● What is the size and characteristics of the data? ● What data management will be required? (e.g. Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL), de-identification, linkage, harmonising, cleaning, quality assurance, archiving and deletion) ● Who will perform the data management and curation? Will the TRE provide this as a service or must incoming data comply with existing standards? ● Will separate storage areas be needed for identified/de-identified data? Who will perform the de-identification? (Provided by TRE or data controller's responsibility)
Technology and Compute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What types of tools, software and packages are required for the management and analysis of the data? Are these compatible with relevant standards and methods, such as the Observational

	<p>Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM), or Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What tools and methods are currently being used / preferred? • What are the scalability and performance needs? • What are the software and infrastructure preferences / requirements? (e.g. open source, commercial, cloud based or local compute, licencing restrictions)
Information Governance & Trust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who are the Data Owner/Controllers responsible for data to be processed in the TRE? • What legal and ethical governance is required from a national level? (e.g. does data need to be hosted in a specific region? Is cross border access allowed?) • What legal and ethical governance is required from a local level? These could include additional requirements from Data Owners/Controllers in addition to national requirements (e.g. what is the legal basis for access?) • What are the data security and privacy requirements for the TRE? • How will Safe Data and Safe Outputs be ensured and maintained? • How will projects be approved and assessed for public benefit? • How will transparency be shown in the data governance and access processes? Are there any standard (e.g. Pan-UK Data Access Transparency Standards) • Who is responsible for researcher accreditation, data approval, output review / disclosure checking? • What certifications or compliance are required? (e.g. ISO9001, ISO27001, HIPAA, Cyber Essentials, etc)
Operational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What partners and stakeholders need to be involved in the design and establishment of the TRE platform? • How long will the platform be maintained? (e.g. programme length or longer) • What capacity building and training needs are required? • What roles and processes are needed for the ongoing operation and maintenance of the system? (e.g. technical support, customer service, data access requests, reviewing committees and panels) • How will the TRE be costed and maintained? • What are the existing infrastructure and software tools available at the institution? (e.g. are there preferred tools, software vendors, or cloud providers?) • What factors influence the development of TRE? (e.g. resources, costs, time, preference for build, open source, buy)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the mechanism or processes by which new infrastructure requirements, software and tools are reviewed and vetted to maintain security whilst enabling innovation?
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Further elements to consider are the opportunities for capacity-building and training activities that will support the delivery and ongoing use of the platform.

Frameworks, such as the [Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments \(SATRE\)](#) specification⁴, provide a thorough and structured approach to identifying the key roles and features required in the development of a TRE solution. Using such frameworks ensures alignment with sector best practices and proven strategies used by other sensitive data projects. Additionally, organisations can use SATRE as a checklist to conduct a self-assessment exercise, helping them determine if they meet the minimum criteria for hosting a TRE, should they choose to follow this route. Details of the SATRE architectural principles are shown below.

Principle	Definition
Usability	A TRE instance that works for all users minimises barriers to use and provides a productive and accessible analysis environment for research.
Maintaining public trust	TREs holding public/sensitive data should build and maintain the trust of data subjects and any other impacted individuals, groups, communities, and organisations by protecting privacy, keeping data secure and being transparent about their work.
Observability	Human initiated and automated processes resulting in change within the TRE should be observable.
Standardisation	TREs should adhere to standards or well-known patterns wherever possible.

Different options for hosting a TRE hosting

TREs can be hosted using a variety of different options, each providing different advantages depending on local needs, infrastructure availability, and resource constraints. The two most common platform designs are cloud hosting and on premise.

Cloud hosting is a popular option as it offers many advantages such as built-in security features, robust disaster recovery capabilities, ability to deploy to other geographies and automated backup functionality. Additionally, cloud services often come with included tools and support for data management, ETL (extract, transform, load), and data ingress/egress. Another advantage is that cloud services are scalable and allow flexibility to adjust resources to dynamically meet demand and scale down during periods of lower utilisation. The major cloud providers, [Microsoft Azure](#), [Amazon Web Services \(AWS\)](#), and [Google Cloud Platform \(GCP\)](#) all provide multiple data regions globally, with some exclusions to regions

⁴SATRE: The Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments is a [DARE UK Driver Project](#)

and functionality. There are also options to apply for specialised cloud credit programmes to support a cloud-based deployment. These include [Microsoft Cloud AI for Good Research Laboratory](#), [AWS World Equity](#), and [Google Cloud for Researchers](#) programmes, which offer cloud infrastructure credits and support for research and initiatives focused on advancing technology for social impact and equity. While these programmes provide valuable resources for active research, they are typically temporary and may not cover long-term infrastructure needs. However, cloud hosting platforms can be disproportionately expensive as they charge based on data size and storage; researchers may incur significant charges (particularly for AI or prediction modelling projects) and organisations providing up-front costing calculations may under-charge without sufficient understanding of the data size and storage requirements. Likewise, cloud hosting platforms do not always provide sufficient support for setting up complex architectures.

In some cases, on-premise solutions may be more cost-effective or feasible, especially where local infrastructure is available and specific security or regulatory requirements make physical control of data necessary. The benefit of on-premise solutions are that they are fully customisable to the specific requirements of the organisation and are maintained locally, which may offer more flexibility and agility for any changes, whether they are improvements or regulatory. Data storage costs are also less expensive than cloud hosting platforms. A challenge with on-premise solutions can be lack of expertise in building, maintaining and improving infrastructure over time, depending on the skill and size of an organisation's networking and infrastructure team. A final option is to use a hybrid model, combining cloud and on-premise infrastructure that offers flexibility by allowing data to move between systems, or through partnerships where institutes with existing infrastructure provide hosting capabilities for others. This can give the customisation benefits of an on-premise solution combined with the ease and scalability of cloud solutions.

Ultimately, the choice of hosting solution, whether cloud, on-premise, or a hybrid approach, should be guided by the specific needs, resources, and regulatory requirements of the institute or region.

Choosing the right approach

The primary options for establishing a new Trusted Research Environment involve either developing a proprietary TRE platform tailored to your specific needs, or customising an existing TRE platform solution offered by a Software as a Service (SaaS) provider to align with the organisation's requirements and objectives. There may also be opportunity to explore options that fall along a spectrum between these two options: for instance, leveraging available open-source setups to develop a TRE or collaborating with a SaaS provider to develop custom features/ configurations that bridge the gap between a fully bespoke solution and an off-the-shelf platform. The following diagram shows the advantages and disadvantages of building vs buying TRE solutions.

The choice between these approaches depends on the programme requirements and other factors such as budgets, technical capabilities, and timeframes. The requirement for more custom or bespoke features will often increase costs and delivery timings; therefore, it is important to carefully understand and weigh the benefits of these features and to take a proportionate approach in their selection. It may also be possible to leverage open-source tooling and resources to lower costs, such as the [DARE UK TREEHOOSE](#) project, which created an open-source infrastructure-as-code template for deploying a minimal TRE based on the health research experience of an established TRE provider. The [Alan Turing Institute's Data Safe Haven](#) also offers an open-source infrastructure-as-code TRE. It is actively used and developed, including its integration into an NHS Secure Data Environment (SDE).

In addition, it is important to consider the supporting services required for the TRE, such as a helpdesk. This should cover the types of support offered, ranging from technical troubleshooting and data wrangling to assistance with code execution and analysis, as well as the availability and scope of these services..

A landscaping and tender process can be undertaken to assess and evaluate different options available for TRE platforms, including available solutions, software vendors and technical partners.

Conclusion

Overall, a Trusted Research Environment platform should align with and advance a research network's objectives, facilitate new research by providing access to data, and foster trust and capacity-building within and across regions.

The HDR UK community and broader partnership networks have contributed to the design and delivery of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) programmes within the UK and

internationally. This collective experience represents a wealth of knowledge that can inform and support future TRE initiatives.

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Supplementary resources

- [Handbook on Statistical Disclosure Control for Outputs](#)
- [Statistical Disclosure Control - Reducing Barriers to Outputs from TREs \(SDC-REBOOT\)](#)
- [EOSC - European Network of Trusted Research Environments \(ENTRUST\)](#)
- [UK Trusted Research Environment Community](#)
- [Pan-UK Data Governance Steering Group Data Access Transparency Standards](#)